

SOCIAL SCIENCIES

FORMATION OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND LOYALTY IN GEORGIAN COMPANIES

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Abstract

Loyalty programs are a prevalent and effective tool for attracting and retaining customers worldwide. They ensure the growth of sales and revenue for companies. Due to their successful outcomes, business representatives in Georgia have started implementing these programs. However, if not managed correctly, loyalty programs can become a complete waste of money despite their numerous positive effects. This paper presents the results of a survey conducted among Georgian consumers. Based on an online survey of 172 respondents, we discussed and analyzed their opinions regarding the proposed loyalty programs and identified the most common flaws and shortcomings.

Keywords: Loyalty programs, consumers, Georgian consumers

In modern business, companies must gather more information about profitable benefits and open communication channels. Every company aims to encourage repeat purchases and thereby increase its competitiveness. This is why reward systems like loyalty programs were created. These discounts and bonuses systems help brands gain their audience's trust, improve their market image, and stand out from competitors. The main goal of planning a loyalty program is to acquire and retain customers for a long time. Its role and importance are evident in the modern business environment. Due to its influence and effectiveness, loyalty programs have become the subject of numerous studies and social groups.

Loyalty programs can create a sense of belonging and trust among customers who feel valued by the brand. They provide businesses with quantitative data on customer behavior, preferences, feedback, and satisfaction, helping companies better understand and segment their customers to tailor products, services, offers, and communications. Loyalty programs can encourage customers to spend more, shop more frequently, and try new products or services, potentially increasing sales, reducing marketing costs, and enhancing profitability. The search for new loyalty program instruments remains a focus of attention. Literature often describes loyalty programs as signals that attract potential customers, significantly impacting consumer decision-making. However, getting community members to participate in these programs is not easy. Several factors directly influence the success of loyalty programs, including the provision of minimum bonuses for new participants and a progressive incentive model where rewards increase with consumption.

Effective loyalty or reward programs require careful planning, implementation, and evaluation to achieve long-term customer retention, satisfaction, and profitability. A loyalty program should be tailored to the

needs, preferences, and behaviors of different customer segments. By using data and analytics, companies can segment their customers based on various criteria, such as purchase frequency, spending level, product category, and channel preference. Personalized offers and communications can then be developed to appeal to each segment and motivate loyalty. Loyalty programs must offer clear and compelling value to customers through attractive and easy-to-use rewards and differentiate themselves from competitors by providing unique and exclusive features.

The purpose of this research is to understand the problems faced by loyalty programs offered by Georgian companies and to determine consumer attitudes. It is essential to study, understand, and address the shortcomings faced by Georgian consumers concerning loyalty programs. To determine the public's awareness and reception of loyalty programs and their benefits, we conducted an online survey consisting of 25 questions, both closed and open-ended. A total of 172 respondents participated in the study.

Among the respondents, 15.1% were under 18, 43.3% were aged 18-24, 27.9% were aged 24-40, 12.8% were aged 40-60, and 2.9% were over 60. Regarding gender distribution, 68% were female, and 32% were male. As for employment status, 39% of respondents were employed, 26.7% were students, 11.6% were self-employed, 10.5% were students (a different category), 9.9% were unemployed, 1.2% were unable to work, and 1.2% were pensioners.

The survey results indicate that while loyalty programs are well-known and widespread globally, Georgian consumers' familiarity with them varies. 58% of respondents had heard about loyalty programs, while 42% were unfamiliar with the term. After providing a brief explanation of loyalty programs within the survey, we found that 53% of respondents used loyalty programs, while 47% did not.

Picture 1. Have you ever used loyalty program?

Pharmacy chains were the most commonly used loyalty programs among Georgian consumers, with 58.1% participation, followed by grocery stores (43.6%), household stores (41.3%), bank programs (23.3%), and hardware stores (17.4%).

Picture 2. What type of loyalty program have you ever used?

Regarding the transparency and simplicity of loyalty programs, most Georgian consumers were not particularly dissatisfied. When asked to rate the transparency of the programs they used, 23% of respondents rated them 5 out of 5, 19% gave a rating of 4, 32% rated them average, and 26% expressed dissatisfaction with low scores.

The majority of respondents preferred points-based loyalty programs, likely due to their familiarity with them. However, 66.3% of respondents indicated that loyalty programs required personal data, which deterred some from participating despite potential benefits. A quarter of respondents reported problems or inconveniences related to providing personal information.

Regarding the complexity of loyalty programs, Georgian users rated them at an average level. It is crucial for participants to understand the benefits they receive from loyalty programs. Only 62.2% of respondents were aware of the benefits they were entitled to. Companies use various methods to disseminate program information, with 80% of respondents preferring to receive information via text messages rather than calls or emails.

The questionnaire included open-ended questions, allowing respondents to express their opinions. Some responses included desires for higher point-to-money equivalents and exclusive programs tailored to high-spending, loyal customers.

The research revealed the shortcomings of Georgian companies' loyalty programs, highlighted the public's level of awareness, and identified necessary approaches for improvement. Developing an effective loyalty program requires significant effort, particularly in developing countries like Georgia, where businesses are still adapting to modern standards and practices. The transition to a market economy has prompted many Georgian companies to adopt global standards and methods that increase revenue and profit. A culture of customer relations has emerged, emphasizing that business success depends on user decisions rather than management alone. A loyalty program is crucial for maintaining long-term relationships between consumers and businesses.

In the study of Georgian loyalty programs, we identified the main factors ensuring the creation of high-quality and effective loyalty programs:

1. **Consumer Research:** To design an effective loyalty program, the consumer market must be studied to understand the specific segment of consumers, targeted by the program.

2. **Clear Definition of Goals:** From the outset, companies should define what they aim to achieve with the rewards program.

3. **Valuable Offers:** The loyalty program should offer valuable and beneficial incentives to ensure user participation.

4. **Simplified Registration:** The registration process should be straightforward and should not require excessive personal information.

5. **Variety of Offers:** Providing diverse and engaging activities and obtaining feedback to maintain active user engagement is essential.

Creating an effective loyalty program involves constant effort and adaptation, particularly in a developing market like Georgia. This research provides insights into consumer attitudes and highlights the steps needed to improve loyalty programs in Georgian companies.

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